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BARTOSZ ARŁUKOWICZ Lessons learnt from the Polish struggle against COVID-19	5	ANJA BAUER COVID-19 in Germany: A hiring crisis	24	STEFFEN JURANEK & FLORIS ZOUTMAN COVID-19: Sweden and its Scandinavian peers	43
MARTIN SEYCHELL EU's international COVID-19 vaccination cooperation	6	ANDRZEJ JARYNOWSKI Phenomenon of participatory "guerilla" epidemiology in post-communist European countries	25	MARIN A. MARINOV Contemporary Denmark: A brief outlook	44
RAUNO MERISAARI & JANETTE SORSIMO Disinformation as human rights challenge	8	KONRAD STAŃCZYK State interventionism in Poland during the COVID-19 crisis	27	OLIVIER RUBIN Decision-making during societal disruptions	46
ALICJA MIKOŁAJEWICZ-WOŹNIAK Two faces of e-health in pandemic times	9	TÍMEA DRINÓCZI & AGNIESZKA BIEŃ-KACAŁA Illiberal constitutionalism and COVID-19 in Poland	28	TORBEN M. ANDERSEN Managing lockdowns and re-openings during the COVID-19 pandemic - The Danish case	47
MUHAMMAD FAHAN BASHIR COVID-19 vaccine and Western pharmaceutical firms: A complex global picture	10	ROBERT KRZYSZTOFIK The COVID-19 epidemic in Poland against the background of multidimensional challenges of the country and society	30	PER LÆGREID Norway's handling of COVID-19	48
DARIUSZ TWORZYDŁO COVID-19 and its impact on the work of experts and public relations specialists in Poland	12	RAFAŁ NAGAJ COVID-19 and energy poverty in Poland	31	DANUTA ANIELA TOMCZAK Combatting pandemics in Norway	49
PETER LUND-THOMSEN Rethinking CSR in global value chains	14	RAFAŁ BOGUSZEWSKI COVID-19 and religiosity in Poland	32	ZHIYANG JIA Labor demand under COVID-19 pandemic in Norway	50
ANDERS ÅSLUND Paradoxes of COVID-19 in Russia	15	KONRAD SOBAŃSKI Fiscal stimulus in Poland during the COVID-19 pandemic: Scope and implications for long-term sustainability	33	M. AURE, L. ASSMUTH, M. HAKKARAINEN & P. M. SIIM Labor migration and translocal families: Mobile lives during the pandemic	51
MARINA LIFSHITS Mortality during the COVID-19 epidemic in Russia	16	RYSZARD KAMIŃSKI & OKSANA POLINKEVYCH Anti-crisis strategies of insurance companies	35	SAJAL KABIRAJ COVID-19 outbreak in Finland: A path to recovery through action-oriented implementation	52
STEPAN ZEMTSOV & VYACHESLAV BABURIN COVID-19 in Russia	17	PAWEŁ NIEDZIÓŁKA Polish banking sector during the COVID-19 crisis – performance and challenges	36	HANNA TIIRINKI Social and health care safety during the COVID-19	53
WESLEY R. MOY Russian misinformation and COVID-19	19	ROBERT ZAJKOWSKI Challenges for Polish family firms tackling the COVID-19 crisis	37	MATTI MÖRTTINEN Managing and communicating corona strategy: A balancing act	54
AGNIESZKA LEGUĆKA Russian disinformation during the pandemic	20	GRZEGORZ ZIMON SMEs and COVID-19 in Poland	39	JUHA PALOKANGAS The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the Finnish forest industry	55
HELI SIMOLA COVID-19 and the Russian economy	21	RACHEL IRWIN Perils of cross-country COVID-19 comparisons	40	TUULA LUOMA Enhancing co-operation in the Baltic Sea Region – together we are stronger	56
MARINA DANILINA Influence of COVID-19 on the labour market in Russia	22	JENS STILHOFF SØRENSEN Sweden's failed pandemic crisis management	41	RINGA RAUDLA Budgetary responses to the COVID-19 pandemic in Estonia	58
JOHANNA MACK Mediatizing the pandemic: COVID-19 and its effects on journalism in Europe and beyond	23				

EXPERT ARTICLES

MERLE ERIKSON	59
What protection does a homeworker need?	
JANA SILAŠKOVA & INGRID PAPPEL	60
How COVID-19 has pushed Estonia towards next generation citizen services	
ALARI PURJU	62
Estonia's governance approaches to the COVID-19	
ANDREY MAKARYCHEV	63
COVID-19 and practical biopolitics: Estonian experiences	
ANDA ROŽUKALNE	65
Two pandemic risks: disinformation and disease	
ALEKSANDRA PALKOVA	66
Disinformation in Latvia - a self- imposed trap of best practices	
VIGITA VĒBRAITĒ	67
Is it possible to protect procedural rights in court proceedings during COVID-19 pandemic (Lithuanian perspective)?	
ANNA MARIA DYNER	68
Belarus — Economic troubles ahead	
ALIAKSEI KAZHARSKI	69
Belarus' prospects after 2020	
LARS ERIK L. GJERDE	70
Lessons from COVID-19 to our politicians	
KARI LIUHTO	71
What before the next pandemic?	

DARIUSZ TWORZYDŁO

COVID-19 and its impact on the work of experts and public relations specialists in Poland

Expert article • 2950

The presented analysis results from research carried out in 2020 within the public relations and media industry. It was conducted at a particular period when the world was fighting the first waves of the pandemic. The research made it possible to identify the changes that have been taking place, which permanently or temporarily would change the scope of the tools used and the relationships established between selected groups of stakeholders. In this study, a synthetic analysis is carried out on projects that concerned both journalists and public relations specialists. It also includes the main conclusions and assessments resulting from the research¹.

The analysis begins with a closer glance at whether PR professionals are concerned about the impact of the restrictions on the performance of their professional duties in public relations agencies. Research conducted at the turn of November and December 2020 jointly with the Association of Public Relations Agencies on employees of agencies affiliated with the Association, indicates that concerns are present among the respondents, but they are not as strong as in the first wave of the coronavirus (March-April 2020). People representing the PR industry, who have experienced functioning in the new reality, get used to the necessary restrictions and the resulting changes. Almost every third respondent has no concerns (31.9%), and every fourth is moderately worried - their fears are lower than during the first wave of the pandemic (26.4%). 13.9% of respondents are as afraid as during the first wave, while 8.8% of respondents are even more afraid. Interestingly, as many as 19% of respondents answered "hard to say" to the question "Are you concerned about the negative impact of the current restrictions related to the COVID-19 pandemic on your PR agency?". Therefore, they were not able to precisely define what their assessment was, which may have been largely due to the fact that the changes taking place in connection with the pandemic are, on the one hand, very dynamic, and, on the other hand, difficult to estimate in terms of long-term effects.

Concerns are a common phenomenon that accompanies the work of people associated with professions that react flexibly to the introduced restrictions. This is also the case with the profession of a specialist or manager dealing with public relations. This problem is visible and important from the perspective of changes taking place in the analyzed industry. Looking at the total percentage of responses indicating the presence of certain concerns (49% in the entire sample), it is worth noting that the scale of their visibility depends on the position held by a person and the length of service. The future of work in the agency is especially disturbing for senior management (72%)² and people with the longest work experience (61.5%). In particular, those people who have already experienced other crises, e.g. economic ones, are able to predict the potential consequences of subsequent events of this type, and COVID-19 is

certainly an unprecedented crisis, an event that the global economy has not experienced so far. Hence, the fears that arise are not only justified but also have rational grounds. Concerns of the surveyed specialists are usually closely related to the assessment of changes that will take place in the future, but also to the issue of forecasts. The concerns mentioned above persist in relation to the research that was carried out in the first months of the pandemic in 2020. In this research project³ public relations specialists were asked to assess how, in their opinion, the market of advisory and communication services will change in the era of the pandemic. The vast majority of respondents (69%) emphasized the need to change the work mode and move to the home office. It was the fastest change that occurred immediately after the outbreak of the pandemic. Not only more duties, but also performing tasks remotely - these are trends that will be more difficult to break. To save costs, many companies have given up expensive offices, reduced their size, and transferred activities partially to the network, dividing employees into groups - those who work in the office and those who can perform their duties remotely. A work rotation system has also been introduced in some entities. A significant reduction in employment was also predicted. In the case of 12% of respondents, the necessity to change the industry became real. The respondents indicated that one of the trends that will continue after the COVID-19 pandemic is brought under control will be the reduction of employment (57.9%). For several months during the pandemic, personnel changes were made in the industry. They were mainly a reaction to adjustments in the number of employees needed to complete the changing structure of projects for clients. During the above-mentioned projects, the respondents also indicated that the pandemic is the most serious crisis that the public relations industry had to deal with in Poland (57.9%).

There is also one additional important observation worth noting. Respondents assessed that for several entities forming the communications industry in Poland, the sequence of events associated with the pandemic is more of an opportunity than a threat (43.0%). The opportunity was seen, among other things, in moving to a higher level of management in terms of using available technological tools, e.g. for conducting meetings, workshops or online conferences, and even operational management. Another favorable circumstance was the possibility to make savings, which are easiest and fastest to implement during crisis events. From the perspective of the changes that are taking place and will continue to take place in the public relations industry, the next opportunity was connected with a very dynamic transition of many clients of the agency towards digital PR, which forced companies to adapt to the new realities and changes occurring on this market. In addition, research has shown that crisis management, CSR, and internal communication activities have started to become increasingly popular on the market. Thus,

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it can be assessed that COVID-19 has indeed caused significant changes in the public relations industry and will force permanent trends. Therefore, companies from the industry will be obliged to adapt to them if their strategic goal is development. ■

1 *The research and analyzes presented in this study were prepared by a team led by prof. Dariusz Tworzydło, composed of: Przemysław Szuba, Marek Zajic, Mateusz Lach, Sławomir Gawroński.*

2 *Chi-square = 14.860; df = 4; p = 0.005; Kramer V = 0.185.*

3 *Exacto's own research from May and April 2020. The aim of the research was to understand the impact of the coronavirus pandemic on the PR industry and to gather views on the future of the industry after the COVID-19 situation is brought under control. Ultimately, 242 PR specialists took part in the survey.*

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